

Electrochemical Behaviour of 1-Thiocarbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one

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Manuscript received 7 April 1993, revised 6 September 1994, accepted 15 September 1994

Pyrazolones¹ are biologically active compounds and have been used as therapeutic agents¹⁻⁵. Similarly sulphonamides are well known for their various physiological activities. In view of the importance of redox phenomenon in the reactions of physiological importance, it was considered worthwhile to know about the mechanism and the nature of end-products as a result of the electroreduction of these potential medicinally important compounds. These studies have been augmented by the results of controlled potential electrolysis and by studying various aspects such as effect of acidity, concentration relevant to their electrochemical behaviour.

Results and Discussion

1-Thiocarbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one reduced to give one well-defined four-electron wave in the pH range 2.0–12.0. This wave has been assigned to the reduction of exocyclic NH–N=C. Other exocyclic sites present in this compound are CO and C=S. The reduction of C=S was excluded by recording polarogram of thiosemicarbazide under identical conditions under which it did not give any polarographic wave. Carbonyl compounds undergo reduction at very high potential² and involve two electrons. Therefore, it can be concluded that the observed four-electron wave is due to the reduction of hydrazono group. The wave-height was proportional to the square root of mercury reservoir height (Table 1) as well as concentration (1.0×10^{-4} to 2.0×10^{-4} M) of the depolariser (Table 2). This suggests the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave. Low values of temperature coefficient (< 1.6% per degree) also supports

the diffusion-controlled nature of the wave. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potentials with in-

TABLE 1—VALUES OF i_d FOR 1-THIOCARBAMEOYL-4-SULPHONAMOYLHYDRAZONO-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE AT VARIOUS HEIGHTS OF MERCURY COLUMN

pH = 8.3, Concn. = 1.0×10^{-4} M

Sl. no.	h cm	\sqrt{h}	i_d μA
1.	60	7.74	0.85
2.	65	8.06	0.90
3.	70	8.36	0.97
4.	75	8.66	1.01

creasing concentration of the depolariser and logarithmic analysis indicate towards the irreversible³ nature of the electrode process and possible role of adsorption. The electrochemical characteristics of the compound in concentration 1.0×10^{-4} M and at pH 8.3 are as follows: $-E_{1/2}$, 0.85 V; $-E_p$, 0.87 V; i_d , 0.85 μA ; $dE_{1/2}/dpH$, 0.042; αn , 1.20; K_{fh}^0 , 9.3×10^{-6} cm s⁻¹. The values of αn and K_{fh}^0 were obtained from the following expressions³,

$$E_{d,e} + 0.2412 = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{fh}^0}{D_0} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} [\log i/(i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$$

The above equation makes it possible to evaluate α from the plots of $E_{d,e}$ vs $[\log i/(i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$.

The half-wave potentials of 1-thiocarbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one were dependent on pH and shifted towards more negative potentials with increase in pH. The plots

of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH were linear upto pH 8.7 and thereafter there was little change in $E_{1/2}$.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF i_d FOR 1-THIOCARBAMOYL-4-SULPHONAMOYLHYDRAZONO-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS

pH = 8.3

Sl. no.	Concn. $\times 10^{-4} M$	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA
1.	0.5	0.83	0.40
2.	1.0	0.85	0.85
3.	1.5	0.87	1.25
4.	2.0	0.88	1.65

Cyclic voltammetry : The cyclic voltammograms of the hydrazone compound in B.R. buffer solutions of different pH were recorded at different scan rates (50 to 200 mV/s) and different concentrations. Cyclic voltammograms exhibited one well-defined cathodic peak (Fig. 1) corresponding to one single step occurring at the electrode surface. This behaviour is in agreement with that observed from polarographic measurements. The linear plot of peak current (i_p) vs square-root of sweep rate ($v^{1/2}$), and i_p vs concentration plot showed little deviation from the origin indicating that the electron reaction was mainly diffusion-controlled⁴ with some adsorption contribution. Peak potential shifted towards negative values with pH linearly upto 8.5, thereafter there was a little change in E_p with pH. The number of electrons taking part in the overall process was calculated from coulometric measurements and found to be four. The adsorption spectra of the depolariser solution before complete electrolysis showed a band at 408 nm which has been attributed to π - π^* electronic transition within the NH-N=C group. After complete electrolysis of the depolariser solution, this band disappeared indicating complete reduction of the NH-N=C group through the consumption of four electrons. The absence of an additional peak in the uv-visible spectra of the solution during electrolysis indicates absence of an absorbing intermediate with sufficient half-life. For coulometric determination⁵ of the number of electrons transferred in the electrode process, 2.0 ml of solution of the compound having buffer, solvent and supporting electrolyte (in the same ratio as was used in a typical polarographic/cyclic voltammetric experiment) was electrolysed by

the application of a potential which corresponds to the limiting current of the polarographic wave. From the decrease of current with time during electrolysis the number of electrons transferred was calculated. Progress of the electrolysis was monitored by recording polarographic reduction wave/cyclic

Fig. 1 Cyclic voltammograms of 1-thiocarbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one at different concentrations : (1) 1.0×10^{-4} ; (2) 1.5×10^{-4} ; (3) $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; $v = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$, pH = 2.5.

voltammograms at different intervals of time, until the reduction wave completely disappeared.

Since the half-wave potentials of the compound under investigation are pH-dependent and the limiting current pH independent upto pH 8.7, it can be concluded that both acidic and basic forms of the compound reached the electrode surface and are electroactive. Thus the proton transfer step preceded⁶ the electrode process.

On this basis of DCP, LSV and CPE, a mechanism is proposed in Scheme 1 for the reduction of this compound.

Scheme 1

The mechanism is supported by the shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative values with pH as protons are consumed in the reduction. As the equilibrium shifts towards the unprotonated form, the $E_{1/2}$ tends to become constant. The plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH shows that above pH 8.7 the shift in $E_{1/2}$ with pH towards negative potential is not so marked as in the acidic pH range. In fact, $E_{1/2}$ becomes constant. This constancy in $E_{1/2}$ may be due to the fact that both the acidic and basic forms of depolariser are electroactive, but in the pH range where the protonation rate decreases, their half-wave potentials are so close to each other that the waves merge⁶.

The half-wave potentials in the pH region defined by $(pK_1 + 1) < pH < (pK_1 - 1)$ are shifted towards more negative values. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ against pH in the region is linear and corresponds to equation,

$$E_{1/2} = C - \frac{RT}{\alpha n F} \ln K_1 + \frac{RT}{\alpha n F} \ln [H^+]$$

At $pH > (pK_1 + 1)$, the half-wave potential of the acidic form is pH-independent and practically equal to the $E_{1/2}$ of the basic form,

$$(E_{1/2})_{HA} = C - \frac{RT}{\alpha n F} \ln k_1 - \frac{RT}{\alpha n F} \ln 0.886 \sqrt{k_1 t_1} - \frac{RT}{\alpha n F} \ln k_1 \approx (E_{1/2})_A$$

The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH is composed of two intersecting linear curves intersecting each other and the pH at the point of intersection of its two linear parts is approximately equal to pK_1 .

Similar steps for the reduction of hydrazono group involving cleavage of the $-N-N-$ bond have also been given by other workers⁷. Due to acid-base equilibrium that exists between two structural forms of the compound,

height of the wave remains pH-independent as long as the formation of the acidic form from the basic form is fast enough, when pH increases, rate of protonation decreases and the wave height decreases as well.

When the polarographic solution was tested after controlled potential electrolysis (cpe), it gave positive dye test thereby confirming the fact that one of the reduction products is an aromatic amine.

Experimental

The polarograms were recorded on an Elico DC CI 25 polarograph with the following capillary characteristics : $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 3.62 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/2}$ at $h = 60$ cm. Saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode. The number of electrons involved in reduction was determined by the method of DeVries and Kroon⁸ using a mercury pool cathode.

Temperature coefficient was determined by Nejedly's method⁹. Polarograms had to be recorded in 35% dimethylformamide due to poor aqueous solubility of these compounds. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded on a BAS-27 cyclic voltammograph attached with a Digital Electronics X-Y/t Omnigraph 2000 recorder. A three-electrode cell was used for the purpose.

The cell consisted of a glass container with a cap having holes for introducing electrodes and tubing of nitrogen gas. Oxygen was removed from the solution by passing nitrogen gas for ~10 min and then a blanket of nitrogen was maintained throughout the experiment. In the present study, glassy carbon (GC) electrode was used as the working electrode. The reference electrode was a Ag/AgCl electrode, and the auxiliary electrode a platinum wire, which was poured directly into the solution. Ag/AgCl electrode was used as a constant potential reference electrode. The GC electrode was polished, washed and activated by triangular voltage sweeps from + 1.0 to -1.5 V at the rate of 5 and 200 mV/s for 15 min. The activity of the electrode was tested¹⁰ for ferricyanide-ferrocyanide in 0.1 M KCl.

Stock solutions (1.0×10^{-3} M) of all the compounds were prepared in dimethylformamide (A.R.), 1.0 M KCl was used as an indifferent electrolyte, so as to maintain the conductivity and to eliminate the effect of migration. B.R. buffer solutions¹¹ of different pH were prepared in distilled water using A.R. grade chemicals. Solutions for electrochemical (DCP and CV) studies were prepared by taking

aliquot (1.0 ml) of stock solution mixed with DMF (2.5 ml), 1 M KCl (1.0 ml) and buffer solution (5.5 ml) of desired pH value. The solutions were deaerated by passing a stream of nitrogen gas for 15 min before recording the polarograms. Each limiting current was corrected by taking a separate polarogram of the blank solution.

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